

IMPORTANT ISSUES OF RAISING THE NATIONAL SPIRIT IN MILITARY SERVANTS

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Abstract: This article discusses the current issues of raising the national spirit among military personnel. It is said that it is the most important duty to be a generation worthy of our ancestors, to adequately protect the borders of our motherland under any conditions, and the importance of the national forum, which is being held to raise the national spirit of military personnel.

Keywords: military serviceman, national spirit, personal composition, descendants, protection, border

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada harbiy xizmatchilarda milliy ruhni yuksaltirishning dolzarb masalalari haqida fikr boradi. Ajdodlarga munosib avlod bo`lish, ona vatanimiz sarhadalarini har qanday sharoitda ham munosib himoya qilish eng asosiy burch ekanligi haqida hamda harbiy xizmatchilarda milliy ruhni yuksaltirish uchun o`tkazib kelinayotgan milliy forumni ahamiyati haqida so`z boradi.

Kalit so`zlar: harbiy xizmatchi, milliy rux, shaxsiy tarkib, avlod-ajdod, himoya, sarhad

The President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Supreme Commander-in-Chief of the Armed Forces Shavkat Mirziyoyev stated in one of his speeches: urur should be strong. National spirit is an invincible force. If the national spirit is strong, the will and fighting potential will be high. Where do our brave children who dream of becoming soldiers in the future get their national spirit and sense of responsibility for the fate of the Holy Motherland? Our country takes from its rich history, from the bravery of our great ancestors such as Amir Temur, Jalaluddin Manguberdi." Indeed, when military personnel have a high national spirit, they will successfully fulfill the tasks assigned to them. Therefore, on February 2, 2019, the concept of moral and spiritual support of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan in order to increase the combat readiness and combat ability of each serviceman in the ranks of the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan, to

ensure the peace and tranquility of our country, the well-being and development of our people was confirmed.

Various forums are being organized in order to coordinate the cooperation activities of the ministry, committees and agencies in the organization of moral and spiritual support, the essence of this concept, the main goal aimed at it. During the past period, a number of scientific researches on the development of the military sector were conducted, internal departmental documents were developed and applied to the troops, and a number of facilities for the moral and spiritual training of military personnel were established. At the forum, which is organized every year, similar works carried out in this field during the past year, achievements and existing shortcomings are critically analyzed. The existing problems of morale and spiritual support in the Armed Forces of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the trend of changing the military and political situation in the world and the region, the uniqueness of the dangers that remain in the Central Asian region, foreign experience in the organization of morale and spiritual support , specific features of the implementation of measures of moral and spiritual support among the population in the event of emergency situations, as well as proposals for coordination of mutual cooperation of ministries and agencies in this regard, are studied. Also, information is being given about the moral and spiritual support of the National Guard troops in order to maintain public safety and eliminate the armed conflict.

Reforms carried out in the army must be related to the interests of the people, this should always be kept in mind, especially when carrying out reforms in the spiritual and moral sphere. The effectiveness of the necessary changes will first of all depend on the laws of military science and the extent to which they rely on the moral laws of armed struggle and war. Only in this way, it will be possible to qualitatively determine the qualitative parameters of the military organization of Uzbekistan, to create it on the basis of traditional and moral traditions.

As vices that are contrary to the moral image of a military serviceman: detachment from life, indifference, indifference, harshness, irresponsibility, ignorance, rudeness, arrogance, censoriousness, arrogance, etc. possible

People have been interested in what is the human spirit and spirituality since time immemorial. There are thousands of definitions. But there is no clear answer. This is a great mystery. Intelligence is not capable of knowing the essence of spirituality. As Uzbek writer Abdulla Avloni said, "spirituality cannot be expressed in one word. He is powerful, rich and dear to us.

In the conditions of new Uzbekistan, as a result of our efforts, the active cooperation of the army and the people, our Armed Forces are literally becoming an integral part of society, a reliable guarantee of the stability and development of our country, and an important institution for educating young people and military personnel in the spirit of patriotism.

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